

Static behavior of two-way lattice dome connected with in-plane flexible joint

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Abstract

The two-way single-layer lattice domes are widely used in large-span building structures since they are lightweight and have a simple shape, making them easy to construct. It is important to consider the response of the two-way single-layer lattice domes with thin members to buckling and earthquake motion. Therefore, this paper focuses on the two-way system for single-layer lattice domes with in-plane flexible joints. It is assumed that the joints are rotatable in planar because the pins connect the intersecting positions of the arches in the orthogonal direction. The arch members can be made continuous and are not separated at the joints. This type of lattice dome can be applied flexibly regarding the number of grid divisions because the joint positions can be freely set. This study evaluates the lattice domes' static characteristics and their feasibility in realization. This type of lattice dome is compared with two-way single-layer domes with rigid joints, revealing the differences.

Keywords: lattice dome, single-layer, two-way, pin-support

1. Introduction

The two-way single-layer lattice domes are widely used in large-span building structures due to their lightweight nature and simple shape, making them easy to construct. However, since single-layer structures generally have relatively low rigidity, it is necessary to consider their response to buckling and earthquake motion carefully. In particular, the joints' structure and division method significantly affect the entire framework's mechanical properties. Therefore, evaluating the static and dynamic characteristics of two-way, single-layer lattice domes is an important issue in structural design.

Previous studies have analyzed two-way single-layer lattice domes' buckling characteristics and static strength. Kato et al. [1], [2] investigated the buckling behavior and ultimate strength evaluation methods for conventional orthogonal grid lattice domes. On the other hand, Satria et al. [3] analyzed the seismic response behavior of single-layer lattice domes with T-joints and clarified their energy absorption characteristics. These studies have considered the effects of rigid joints and unique connections, highlighting the significant influence of joint structures on the seismic performance and stability of lattice domes.

This paper aims to improve constructability by evaluating the static strength of a new type of single-layer lattice dome with flexible joints. Unlike T-joints, this structure adopts pin connections, which simplify construction. F. Tayeb et al. [4] conducted a construction experiment on a hypothetical dome using such joints. Furthermore, by comparing conventional two-way single-layer domes with rigid joints, this paper clarifies the effects of joint flexibility on the overall strength and stability of the structure. Based on these perspectives, this research examines the feasibility of realizing this new type of two-way single-layer lattice dome.

2. Analytical model

In this paper, domes are two-way lattices. Autodesk Inventor Nastran 2025 is used for this analysis. Figure 1 shows the configuration of an analytical model for the dome. Table 1 shows the geometrical properties of the dome. The dome is based on a dome with $R = 22$ m and $\Phi = 60^\circ$. The dome offsets the radius R of the base dome by 0.08 m inside and outside. Inside are the X -direction arch members, while outside are the Y -direction arch members. The X -direction and Y -direction arch members do not intersect because they have different R s. The X -direction and Y -direction arch members have the same height, H_0 , from the center point (C.P.) to the ground line (G.L.) (= 11 m). Both the X -direction and Y -direction arch members are arranged at 6° intervals. The dome structure consists of 19 arch members and supporting members in both the X -direction and Y -direction. The supporting members at the boundary are pin-supported. The arch members are made continuous and are not separated at the joints. The arch members in this analysis are modeled as beam elements. Also, the element size (beam element length) is set to 0.25 m to approximate the curve with acceptable straight segments.

Figure 1: Configuration of an analytical model for the dome

Table 1: Geometrical properties of the dome

	ϕ [deg]	θ [deg]	R [m]	L [m]	H_0 [m]	H [m]
Base	60	6	22	38.11	11	11
X	59.88	6	21.92	37.97	11	10.92
Y	60.12	6	22.08	38.24	11	11.08

Table 2 shows the material properties of the dome's arch members. All arch members are made of STK400E. The load is a uniformly distributed load and is applied to all joints (outside nodes) of the Y -direction arch members. Nodal load is set at $P = 10$ kN/node. In this case, the total number of loading nodes is 349.

Table 2: Material properties of the dome's arch members

D [mm]	t [mm]	A [mm ²]	I [mm ⁴]	E [N/mm ²]
101.6	5.7	1717	1.98×10^6	2.05×10^5

Figure 2 shows the simplified diagram of the arch members and joints. The joints have outside node, inside node, and intermediate node between them. The following shows the calculation formula for the node coordinates of the joints. Equations (3) and (4) are derived from the rotation matrices in equations (1) and (2). Also, equation (5) is the equation of a sphere. By solving these equations, the node coordinates at the joints are calculated. In this case, the outside node and the inside node are connected by rigid joints.

$$n_{\theta_x} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \theta_x & 0 & \sin \theta_x \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ -\sin \theta_x & 0 & \cos \theta_x \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \theta_x \\ 0 \\ -\sin \theta_x \end{bmatrix} \quad (1)$$

$$n_{\theta_y} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \cos \theta_y & \sin \theta_y \\ 0 & -\sin \theta_y & \cos \theta_y \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \cos \theta_y \\ -\sin \theta_y \end{bmatrix} \quad (2)$$

$$\cos \theta_x \cdot x - \sin \theta_x \cdot z = 0 \quad (3)$$

$$\cos \theta_y \cdot y - \sin \theta_y \cdot z = 0 \quad (4)$$

$$x^2 + y^2 + z^2 = R^2 \quad (5)$$

Table 3 shows the material properties of the dome's joint members. The arch members are connected by round bars ($D = 50$ mm). The joints are made flexible by reducing their torsional rigidity, J . As

shown in Figure 2 (b), three types of joints with different torsional rigidities, $J = 6.14 \times 10^5$, 3.00×10^5 , 1 mm^4 , are considered for comparison. Also, a two-way single-layer lattice dome is compared to clarify the effects of flexible joints. The joints between the X -direction and Y -direction arches are rigid in this case. To understand the impact of joint differences among these four types of domes.

Figure 2: Simplified diagram of the arch members and joints

Table 3: Material properties of the dome's joint members

d [mm]	A [mm ²]	I [mm ⁴]	E [N/mm ²]	J [mm ⁴]
50	1963	3.09×10^5	2.05×10^5	6.14×10^5

3. Analytical result

Figures 3~6 show the target structure's deformation, axial force distribution, bending moment, and stress distribution. On the graph's horizontal axis, AO represents half of the X -direction arch members (Inside members), while OD represents half of the Y -direction arch members (Outside members). The bending moment M is calculated from Equation (6). The stress σ is calculated from Equation (7). In this stress σ , the bending stress is obtained by taking the difference, as all axial forces N are negative values.

$$M = \sqrt{M_x^2 + M_y^2} \quad (6)$$

$$\sigma = \frac{N}{A} - \frac{M}{I / \frac{D}{2}} \quad (7)$$

The deformation is examined. In all domes, the central part of the arches undergoes a downward deformation. The apex of the arch is the point of maximum deformation. Also, as the torsional rigidity decreases, the deformation increases. Compared to the rigidly connected dome, the dome with $J = 6.14 \times 10^5 \text{ mm}^4$ shows approximately twice the deformation, while the dome with $J = 1 \text{ mm}^4$ shows approximately 2.5 times the deformation. As the torsional rigidity decreases, the entire arch becomes more flexible, causing the dome's deformation to be more significant locally.

Figure 3: Deformation

Figure 4: Axial force distribution

Figure 5: Bending moment distribution

Figure 6: Stress distribution

The axial force distribution is examined. In all domes, the arch ends show a maximum compressive axial force of approximately 50 kN (10 kN/node). In this case, only a slight difference in axial force N is observed due to changes in torsional rigidity.

The bending moment distribution is examined. In all domes, the arch ends show a maximum bending moment of approximately 2 kNm. Also, as the torsional rigidity decreases, the bending moment at the center of the arch increases. On the other hand, in the X -direction arch members, when the torsional rigidity is low, the bending moment at the arch ends slightly decreases. The bending moment is distributed throughout the arch when the torsional rigidity is low.

4. Conclusion

This paper analyzed the static behavior of a two-way single-layer lattice dome with in-plane flexible joints. The results showed that as the torsional rigidity of the joints decreased, the overall deformation increased. Also, the bending moment at the arch center increased as the torsional rigidity decreased. Meanwhile, the axial force distribution remained almost unchanged regardless of joint rigidity. These results indicate that adopting in-plane flexible joints in a two-way single-layer lattice dome increases its flexibility compared to a rigidly connected dome by reducing torsional rigidity.

References

- [1] Yamashita T., and Kato S., *Elastic buckling characteristics of two-way grid shells of single layer and its application in design to evaluate the non-linear behavior and ultimate strength*, Journal of Constructional Steel Research, Vol.57, No.12, pp.1289-1308, 2001.6
- [2] Kato S., Yamashita T., *Evaluation of Elasto-Plastic Buckling Strength of Two-Way Grid Shells Using Continuum Analogy*, International Journal of Space Structures, Vol.17, No.4, pp.249-261, 2002.12
- [3] Satria E., Kato S., Nakazawa S., and Kakuda D., *Study on the dynamic behavior of a new type of two-way single layer lattice dome with nodal eccentricity*, Steel and Composite Structure, Vol.8, No.6, pp.511-530, 2008.11
- [4] F. Tayeb, J. -F. Caron, O. Baverel, L. Du Peloux, *Stability and robustness of a 300 m² composite gridshell structure*, Construction and Building Materials, Vol.49, pp.926-938, 2013.12